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Haematological Indices of Broiler Starter Chicks Fed Doum Palm Extract as Alternative to Antibiotics

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ABSTRACT

This experiment was carried out to investigate the haematological indices of broiler starter chicks fed different levels of Doum palm extract. The experiment lasted for 28 days and a total of 300 – 1-day old broiler chicks (Ross 308) were randomly distributed into five treatments with six replicates consisting of ten birds each in a completely randomized design. Standard diet was adequate in all nutrients according to the requirement of broilers by NRC (1994). Birds in treatment 1 was fed standard diet without doum palm extract, treatment 2 (standard diet with neomycin at 0.2 grams per liter of water), treatment 3, 4 and 5 were fed same diet with doum palm extract at 0.2 mL, 0.4 mL and 0.6 mL in that order. Feed and fresh clean water were provided at all times. Analysis of phyto-constituents in doum palm extract showed that it contained a higher concentrations of phenol (58.70 mg/g) followed by flavonoids (47.72 mg/g), terpenoids (32.86 mg/g), tannins (28.06 mg/g), alkaloids (25.29 mg/g) and saponins (12.50 mg/g). Red blood cell, haemoglobin, pack cell volume, mean corpuscular volume, mean corpuscular haemoglobin concentration, white blood cell, lymphocytes, heterophils, eosinophils and monocytes count follow similar pattern and were higher among birds fed treatment 3, 4 and 5, intermediate in treatment 2 and lower in treatment 1 ($P < 0.05$). However, values recorded were within the reference range for healthy broiler chick. In conclusion, doum palm extract are rich in phyto-constituents with numerous pharmacological properties and can be fed to birds up to 0.6 mL per liter without compromising their health status.

Keywords: Broilers; Blood; Doum palm; Phyto-constituents; Neomycin; Haematology.

1. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, the idea of reducing antibiotic prophylaxis in animal feed is gaining traction around the world. However, antibiotic addition has reduced the incidence of some diseases, boosted growth rate, and enhanced feed efficiency in animal production (Liz, 2020; Laura, 2021). However, there is growing proof that such long-term antibiotic use causes bacterial resistance, which has a severe impact on the future efficacy of important medications (Laura, 2021). As a result, numerous nations have prohibited the use of antibiotics in animal feed (Sandra, 2021; Ines, 2022). This adds urgency to the hunt for alternate techniques to sustain animal performance and prevent animals from illness (Liz, 2021). Some of possible options is the administration of medicinal plants, which have fewer side effects than synthetic drugs because they contain phyto-constituents with important pharmacological properties such as antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, antiviral, antioxidant, antifungal, cytotoxic, immunostimulatory, and so on (John, 2024). Hyphaene thebaica, often known as doum, is a dioecious, dichotomous, and arborescent Arecaceae palm (Orwa et al., 2009; Faten, 2009). The tree is drought-resistant, endemic to North Africa, and can reach heights of 17 meters (Moussa et al., 1998; Hsu et al., 2006). Among the potential alternatives is the use of medicinal plants which exhibits lower side effects compared to synthetic drugs due to the presence of phyto-constituents in them which has important pharmacological properties like, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, antiviral, antioxidant, antifungal, cytotoxic, immuno-stimulatory amongst others (John, 2024).

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Phytochemical evaluation of doum fruit revealed the presence of triterpenoids, glycosides, flavonoids, alkaloids, phenols, xanthone, steroids, coumarins, glycol-peptides amongst others (Muhammad et al., 2022; Abdulsalam et al., 2018). According to Faten (2009), extracts from doum fruits can inhibit the activities of some pathogenic organisms such as *Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Aspergillus spp* and *Penicillium notatum*. Traditionally, the extract from the fruit can be used for the treatment of sores, gastrointestinal disorder, headache, toothache and general body pain (Reda, 2015; Bonde et al., 1990). In broilers, in vivo antimicrobial efficacy of plant extracts on *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella spp*, *Staphylococcus spp*, *Shigella spp*, *Clostridium spp* amongst others was demonstrated (Oloruntola et al., 2016; John, 2024; Dhan et al., 2007). Furthermore, in a report made by Mushtaq et al. (2012); Agubosi et al. (2022); Liz (2020), it is mentioned that some plant extracts can promote the activities of endogenous enzymes in the gastro intestinal tract and improve haemoglobin, red blood cell, pack cell volume, white blood cells and their differentials. However, there is little or no report on feeding doum palm extract on the haematological parameters of broiler chicks. This research is timely, because the increasing state of antimicrobial resistance is alarming, doum palm extract can be fed to birds to safeguard the future use of antibiotics, promote livestock sustainability and food safety. This research was designed to determine the haematological indices of starter broiler chicks fed doum palm extract as alternative to antibiotics.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Experiment location

Poultry unit of Sumitra Research Institute Gujarat was used for the study. It was carried out between October to December, 2023 according to the ethical procedures and guidelines at the Department of Animal Nutrition and Biochemistry (AA/009D/2022). Sumitra Research Institute is situated between 28° 18' N and 70° 35' E India.

2.2. Collection and preparation of doum palm extract

Dried doum palm fruit was harvested within Sumitra Research Institute, Gujarat, India. The epicarp of the fruit was removed into a tray with a sharp kitchen knife and grounded into powder using an electric blender. 200 grams of grinded powder is soaked into 1000 mL of ethanol for 2 days, stirred at different interval before it was soaked with Whatman filter paper to obtain doum palm extract. 100 mL of the filtered extract was sent to the laboratory for further evaluation.

2.3. Evaluation of phyto-constituents in doum palm extract

The laboratory procedures recently published by (Alagbe, 2024) were used for the determination of total phenols, tannins, alkaloids, saponins, flavonoids and terpenoids. Plant were examined at different optical density for quantification using a gas chromatography-mass spectrometry at 460 nm, 550 nm, 400 nm, 620 nm, 601 nm and 450 nm respectively. GC/MS Tripod (Model 81W-009C, China) was used and maintained to an inlet temperature of 406°C, scan rate of 12,000 amu/seconds, mass range (2.00 – 1,500 amu), filament emission current (400 µA) and pressure range of 120 psi to obtain an accurate result.

2.4. Proximate examination of experimental diet

Near infra-red kit (Model: ROSS NIRSTM, China) was used to analyze experimental diet. 100 grams of sample was placed in the sample tray of the kit after calibration. Result was obtained within 60 seconds and printed out from the visual display unit. To ensure precision in results, optical band, data resolution and wavelength was maintained at 8.10 nm, 0.4 nm and 2000 nm respectively.

2.5. Experimental birds and their management

300 – 1-day old (Ross 308) broiler chicks were used for the experiment. A battery cage measuring 560 cm by 400 cm by 150 cm (Length × width × height) equipped with nipple drinker and manual feeder was disinfected with Morigad® two weeks before the commencement of the experiment. The cages are placed in a clean disinfected open sided pen measuring 15 meters (length) by 10 meters (width). On arrival of chicks, their average body weight was taken using a digital sensitive scale before they were distributed into five treatments with six replicates consisting of ten birds each in a completely randomized design. Birds were placed on anti-stress (Glucomol® plus miavit super®) for 3 days and fed standard diet which is adequate in all nutrients required by broilers (NRC, 1994). Chicks in treatment 1 (T₁) was fed standard diet without doum palm extract, treatment 2 (T₂) was fed standard diet with 0.2 grams' neomycin per liter of water while treatment 3 (T₃), 4 (T₄) and 5 (T₅) were fed same diet with doum palm extract at 0.2 mL, 0.4 mL and 0.6 mL per liter of water. Feed and fresh clean water was fed at all time and light was provided on a continuous basis. Trial lasted for 28 days under strict management procedures. Weighing of birds was subsequently done weekly before the birds were fed in the morning. Feed intake was estimated as the difference between left over and feed served.

2.6. Blood collection and analysis

On the 28th day of the experiment, 2 mL of blood was collected from the wing veins of 12 randomly selected birds for haematological analysis. Samples were collected into a labeled bottle with anticoagulant and placed in an ice pack before it was transferred to the laboratory. Laboratory analysis of blood was carried out using Sysmex automated blood analyzer (Model

FH/097/LG, China). Kit was maintained at an ambient temperature of 18 – 32°C and humidity of 80 % to ensure accuracy in result.

2.7. Statistical analysis

All the data were subjected to one-way ANOVA using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25. The differences among the treatment means were determined ($P < 0.05$) by Duncan multiple range test of SPSS.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the ingredients and chemical composition of experimental diet as ready reference.

Table 1: Ingredients and chemical composition of experimental diet

Ingredients	Treatment 1	Treatment 2	Treatment 3	Treatment 4	Treatment 5
	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)
Yellow corn	53.00	53.00	53.00	53.00	53.00
Wheat bran	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00
Soybean meal	26.50	26.50	26.50	26.50	26.50
Groundnut meal	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00
Fish meal (Imported: 72%)	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00
Limestone	1.50	1.50	1.50	1.50	1.50
Bone meal	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00
Methionine	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Lysine	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.20
**Mineral/Vitamin Premix	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Salt	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Toxin binder	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05
Neomycin (g/kg)	0.00	0.20	-	-	-
Doum extract (mL/liter)	-	-	0.20	0.40	0.60
Total	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
Analyzed analysis (% dry matter)					
Crude protein (%)	23.47	23.47	23.47	23.47	23.47
Crude fibre (%)	3.56	3.56	3.56	3.56	3.56
Ether extract (%)	3.20	3.20	3.20	3.20	3.20
Calcium (%)	1.49	1.49	1.49	1.49	1.49
Phosphorus (%)	0.58	0.58	0.58	0.58	0.58
Metabolizable energy (MJ/kg)	12.00	12.00	12.00	12.00	12.00

Note: **Mineral-vitamin premix (2.5 kg) contains; Thiamine, 12000 mg, riboflavin, 8000 mg, pyridoxine, 6000 mg, cyanocobalamin, 2000 mg, niacin, 28,000 mg, D-panthotenate, 12,000 mg, folic acid, 600 mg, biotin, 2500 mg, cholecalciferol, 2,400,000 iu., tocopherol acetate, 25,000 iu., ascorbic acid, 62,000 mg, manganese, 56mg, iron, 70,200 mg, 300 mg, iodine, 200 mg, selenium, 85 mg, choline chloride, 46,000 mg

Figure 1 revealed that doum palm extract contained a higher concentration of phenolic compound (58.70 mg/g) followed by flavonoids (47.72 mg/g), terpenoids (32.86 mg/g), tannins (28.06 mg/g), alkaloids (25.29 mg/g) and saponins (12.50 mg/g). This result showed that possess several medicinal or therapeutic properties. The result recorded in this experiment confirms the earlier report of Ademola et al. (2009); House et al. (2001). According to Ojediran et al. (2024), age of plant, method of extraction, species amongst others could affect the composition of phyto-constituents in medicinal plant. The medicinal property of herbs is due to the presence of different complex chemical substance as secondary metabolites, which are exclusively accumulated in different parts of the plants, (Hussain et al., 2010). These secondary metabolites are important as potential antimicrobial crude drug and source for natural compounds as new anti-infection agents (Dwivedi et al., 2011). For instance, phenolic compounds have been suggested to have antimicrobial and antioxidant properties (Yadav et al., 2010; Xu and Chang, 2007). Alkaloids have been reported to perform antimalarial, analgesics and antibacterial roles (Valgas et al., 2007). Saponins are also important therapeutically as they are shown to have hypolipidemic and anticancer activity (Tenover, 2006). Flavonoids and terpenoids are capable of scavenging free radicals, preventing cardiovascular disease and sometimes are anti-inflammatory agents (Samy and Ignacimuthu, 2000; Alagbe, 2023).

Figure 1: Phytochemical composition of Doum palm extract

Effect of doum palm extract on the haematological parameters of broiler starter chicks is presented in Table 2. Red blood cell, pack cell volume, haemoglobin, mean corpuscular volume, mean corpuscular haemoglobin, mean corpuscular haemoglobin concentration, white blood cell, lymphocytes, monocytes, heterophils and eosinophil count follow similar pattern and were significantly ($P < 0.05$) influenced by the treatment. Birds fed treatment 3 (0.2 mL doum palm extract per liter of water) were similar ($P > 0.05$) to those fed treatment 4 (0.4 mL doum palm extract per liter of water) and treatment 5 (0.6 mL doum palm extract per liter of water) but significantly higher ($P < 0.05$) than those fed treatment 2 (0.2 grams' neomycin per liter of water) and control (treatment 1: without antibiotics). Red blood cell, haemoglobin and pack cell volume count which varied from $1.93 - 3.11 (\times 10^{12}/L)$, $7.13 - 12.31$ g/dL and $25.17 - 31.06$ % were within the values $2.03 - 3.55 (\times 10^{12}/L)$, $7.00 - 13.00$ g/dL and $25.00 - 32.00$ % cited by Thall (2007); Talebi et al. (2007). However, lower values (pack cell volume; $23.81 - 30.02$ %, red blood cell; $1.88 - 2.30 (\times 10^{12}/L)$ and haemoglobin; $6.00 - 10.02$ g/dL) were recorded by Alagbe (2022) when *Albizialebeck* stem bark aqueous extract was fed to broiler chicks. This variation could be attributed to breed or age of birds. The result recorded on red blood cell, haemoglobin and pack cell volume count revealed that the presence of phyto-constituents in doum palm extract as presented in Table 2 helped to improve these parameters. Improvement in red blood cell, haemoglobin and pack cell volume count in treatment 3, 4 and 5 showed that the birds had no iron deficiency (Adewale et al., 2021). Low red blood cell suggests bone marrow disorder, metabolic disorder, chronic inflammation and gastrointestinal infections (Alagbe and Grace, 2019; Alagbe et al., 2019). Pack cell volume can be used to diagnose polycythemia, dehydration and other health conditions (Daniel et al., 2023; John, 2024). Mean corpuscular volume values took the form of $(99.19 - 123.7$ fl), mean corpuscular haemoglobin ($30.14 - 42.75$ pg) and mean corpuscular haemoglobin concentration ($27.13 - 35.85$ g/dL) values were within the normal range ($87.00 - 150.00$ pg), ($28.10 - 45.00$ pg) and $25.00 - 50.00$ g/dL reported by John (2024); Islam et al. (2004). Low mean corpuscular volume, mean corpuscular haemoglobin and mean corpuscular haemoglobin concentrations indicate folate or iron deficiency in birds (John, 2024; Jain, 1986). White blood cell, lymphocytes, monocytes, heterophils, eosinophils count varied from $8.92 - 17.04 (\times 10^9/L)$, $54.18 - 71.89$ %, $0.67 - 1.45$ %, $28.64 - 38.17$ % and $0.51 - 1.11$ % correspondingly. These values were within the normal range $8.00 - 25.00 (\times 10^9/L)$, $45.00 - 80.00$ %, $0.50 - 2.00$ % and $0.50 - 1.00$ % recorded by Jain (1993). White blood cell count is low during chronic infection, liver disease and mineral, vitamin deficiency (Riddell, 2011; John, 2024). Monocytes are part of the immune system that prevents the entry of pathogens in the body (Daniel et al., 2023). The result obtained in this experiment is in agreement with the findings of Mushtaq et al. (2012), when *Withaniasomnifera* leaf extract was administered to broiler chicks at 20 grams per liter of water. Similar observation was recorded by Abd-El Hack et al. (2015) who reported an improvement in red blood cell, haemoglobin and white blood count of birds fed thyme powder.

Table 2: Effect of doum palm extract on the haematological parameters of broiler starter chicks

Variables	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄	T ₅	SEM
Red blood cell ($\times 10^{12}/L$)	1.93 ^c	2.61 ^b	3.00 ^a	3.04 ^a	3.11 ^a	0.13
Pack cell volume (%)	25.17 ^c	28.89 ^b	30.80 ^a	30.87 ^a	31.06 ^a	0.56
Haemoglobin (g/dL)	7.13 ^c	9.02 ^b	12.00 ^a	12.06 ^a	12.31 ^a	0.27
Mean corpuscular volume (fl)	99.19 ^c	102.1 ^b	121.4 ^a	123.0 ^a	123.7 ^a	2.93
Mean corpuscular haemoglobin (pg)	30.14 ^b	30.80 ^b	42.16 ^a	42.60 ^a	42.75 ^a	0.87
Mean corpuscular haemoglobin conc. (g/dL)	27.13 ^b	28.21 ^b	34.08 ^a	35.19 ^a	35.85 ^a	0.74
White blood cell ($\times 10^9/L$)	8.92 ^c	10.44 ^b	16.40 ^a	16.93 ^a	17.04 ^a	0.11
Lymphocytes (%)	54.18 ^c	60.02 ^b	70.18 ^a	71.12 ^a	71.89 ^a	1.25
Eosinophils (%)	0.51 ^b	0.62 ^b	1.00 ^a	1.02 ^a	1.11 ^a	0.03
Heterophils (%)	28.64 ^b	28.74 ^b	37.92 ^a	38.04 ^a	38.17 ^a	0.51
Monocytes (%)	0.67 ^b	1.72 ^b	1.20 ^a	1.41 ^a	1.45 ^a	0.01

Note: Means on the same row having different superscripts are significantly different ($P < 0.05$);

T₁: Standard diet without antibiotics; T₂: standard diet with 0.2-gram neomycin/liter of water; T₃, T₄ and T₅: standard diet with doum palm extract at 0.2 mL, 0.4 mL and 0.6 mL per liter of water.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, doum palm extract contains several phyto-constituents with numerous pharmacological properties. These chemicals are safe, environmentally friendly and could be fed to broiler chicks up to 0.6 mL per liter of water without compromising the health status of birds.

Ethical approval

All international standards have been adopted and compliance.

Informed consent

The study was conducted with equal participation by all authors.

Conflicts of interests

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interests.

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The study has not received any external funding.

Data and materials availability

All data associated with this study are present in the paper.

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